

Wastewater Surveillance AMELAG - Weekly Report

[Robert Koch Institute](#), & [Federal Environment Agency](#)

Cite

Robert Koch Institute, & Federal Environment Agency. (2026). Wastewater Surveillance AMELAG - Weekly Report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21105156>

Abstract

The interactive report “Wastewater Surveillance AMELAG - Weekly Report” of the Robert Koch Institute and the Federal Environment Agency illustrates data from the monitoring of infectious pathogens in wastewater. Data on SARS-CoV-2 viral load has been collected since February 2022 in a nationwide network of wastewater treatment plants, laboratories and local authorities. Since then, the data has been supplemented by the viral load of other respiratory viruses (Influenza A/B, RSV). In addition to individual values from the wastewater treatment plants, the report also contains population-weighted, aggregated time series.

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Information on the context of origin

In AMELAG (“Abwassermonitoring für die epidemiologische Lagebewertung”, German for wastewater monitoring for epidemiological situation assessment) local authorities, wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) and laboratories are working together to take, analyze and evaluate wastewater samples. The project aims at testing wastewater samples for selected pathogens and to establish this as an additional indicator for the epidemiological situation assessment at state and federal level. Currently, wastewater samples from selected treatment plants are being tested for SARS-CoV-2, influenza viruses and respiratory syncytial viruses (RSV). This data is interactively visualized and contextualized in the “Wastewater Surveillance AMELAG - Weekly Report”.

Interactive report and data provision

Here you find the interactive weekly report with the epidemiological evaluations of the wastewater monitoring data.

[Wastewater Surveillance AMELAG - Weekly Report](#)

It is based on the AMELAG wastewater surveillance data, which is available as open data:

Robert Koch-Institut, & Federal Environment Agency. (2026). Wastewater Surveillance AMELAG [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10782701>

Administrative and organizational information

AMELAG is a project funded by the [Federal Ministry of Health \(BMG\)](#) and is being conducted in cooperation with the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and [Consumer Protection \(BMUV\)](#). The project is being carried out jointly by the Robert Koch Institute (RKI) and the [Federal Environment Agency \(UBA\)](#). Further information on AMELAG can be found on the [project website](#).

The participating WWTPs are responsible for taking samples, which are analyzed by the participating laboratories. In addition to commercial laboratories, state laboratories and the Federal Environment Agency, the Central Medical Service of the German Armed Forces also carries out part of the analysis.

Some of the WWTPs and laboratories are also involved in wastewater surveillance projects in the federal states or in other research projects.

The company [ENDA](#) was commissioned with data management. The data collected are stored and processed in a database (PiA-Monitor).

The interactive report is prepared by [Unit 32 | Surveillance](#) in collaboration with Unit [MF 2 | Domain Specific Data Competence Centre](#).

The report is edited and published by the Unit [MF 4 | Domain Specific Data and Research Data Management](#). Questions about data management and the publication infrastructure can be directed to the Open Data team of the MF4 department at OpenData@rki.de.

Metadata

To increase findability, the provided interactive report is described with metadata. The metadata are distributed to the relevant platforms via GitHub Actions. There is a specific metadata file for each platform; these are stored in the metadata folder:

| [Metadaten/](#)

Versioning and DOI assignment are performed via [Zenodo.org](#). The metadata prepared for import into Zenodo are stored in the [zenodo.json](#). Documentation of the individual metadata variables can be found at <https://developers.zenodo.org/#representation>.

| [Metadaten/zenodo.json](#)

Guidelines for reuse of the report

This interactive reports published by the RKI is available on [Zenodo.org](#), [GitHub.com](#), and [OpenCoDE](#):

- <https://zenodo.org/communities/robertkochinstitut>
- <https://github.com/robert-koch-institut>
- <https://gitlab.opencode.de/robert-koch-institut>

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